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Master's thesis:

Dividend policy in Russia: theory and applications

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Abstract

In this paper the research concentrated on the dividend policy of Russian firms. The Modigliani-Miller issue whether dividends are irrelevant was subject to empirical analysis which has shown that MM is wrong and that dividend policy does have impact on the performance of companies and stock price. Another issue raised was the dividend policy per se. The factors which can have impact on dividend policy were focused on and analyzed. Among the most important factors influencing the dividend policy were the sector in which a company operates, ownership structure, together with current indicators of performance, such as current profit and the amount of long term debt a company attracts for financing.

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Dividend policy in Russia: theory and applications

1. Introduction

The development of Russian stock market began soon after market reforms. The process of privatization led to the formation of the owners of companies. There were several ways of privatization proposed by the government, but the privatization ended up with a variant where employees and directors were given more favorable rights what concerns ownership in their company. All members of a company were given a right to purchase shares of their own firm and this share depended to a great extent upon the position of an employee. In the result large part of ownership was concentrated in the hands of top managers who can determine the policy of company's operations having the dominant position in the board of directors and in the meeting of shareholders. That in turn led to some peculiarities in investment and other policies of the companies and especially in so-called "dividend policy" of newly formed market type enterprises. As it is shown in this paper dividend ratio, which is the ratio of dividend paid out if net profit is now far lower in Russia than it is in established Western securities markets, although some convergence did occur over time. Perfunctory view on this issue can find among the reasons why does it happen perhaps the most simple one, that is top managers of a company just do not have to pay dividends at all. This is a cause of their dominant position in a company which can lure themselves to retain all the earnings and consume costly perquisites. The idea fits especially well in the sectors where the most deep recession has occurred, e.g., consumer goods. The inability of the shareholders to change the policy of a company and to force directors to pay higher dividends stems in turn from the fact that large portions of outside shares (shares not hold by management and employees) are concentrated in the hands of large financial institutions, especially western ones, many of them being interested not in strategic control over the firm but in short term speculative goals.

All this facts led to dividend policy of Russian firms being even more complex and confused issue than it is in the West, where theory of why and how dividends are paid is still far from being

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developed, although a lot of seminal contributions were made by Lintner [1956], Gordon [1959] and Miller & Modigliani [1961]. This research conducted in the framework of NES project "Financial markets in economies in transition" tries to incorporate recent developments and methodology of modern finance theory to Russian stock markets and to check for the explanatory power in the aspect of dividend policy of major Russian companies. Because the market for the traded stocks in Russia exists for quite a short period of time and it is still far from being established in the way we can observe in developed industrial countries, we can put a priori a hypothesis that a more elaborate theory should be developed to explain the behavior of the major indicators of Russian companies, one of which is undoubtedly the dividend policy of a firm.

2. Stylized facts

One of the major aspect in the modern theory of finance is the dividend policy the firms' managers choose in their operations. The importance of the dividend policy stems from several very important considerations. First the dividend policy the managers choose is one of the major financial decisions. Another reason is that the proper understanding of dividend policy is crucial to many other areas of financial economics. Particularly, theories of asset pricing, capital structure and capital budgeting, mergers and acquisitions rely heavily on a view why and how dividends are paid.

There are a number of stylized facts that play a very significant role in the study of dividend policy:

1. Corporations typically pay out a significant share of their earnings as dividends.
2. Over the history, dividends played the predominant role in the distribution of a firm's earnings; share repurchases were relatively unimportant until the mid 1980s.
3. Individuals in high tax brackets receive large amounts in dividends and pay substantial amounts of taxes on these dividends.
4. Corporations try to smooth the stream of dividends.
5. The market reacts positively to announcements of dividend increases and negatively to announcements of dividend decreases.

The first observation that corporations pay a substantial amount of their profits in the form of dividends is supported by the figures. For the U. S corporations the share of after-tax profits paid in

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the form of dividends was between 50 and 70% for the period from 1971 through 1992, as compared with a range of 40 to 60% in earlier years.

The second observation is supported by the figures, and a number of features should be mentioned. First it should be noticed that for large firms, the percentage paid is somewhat lower and also somewhat stable when payout is measured as a percentage of net income (as opposed to after-tax corporate profits). In the 1980s, it was usually between 40 and 50%, compared to 30 and 40% in the 1970s. As Bagwell & Shoven [1989] stress, there was an important change in 1984 and 1985 in the repurchases made by corporations. Before that time, the amount repurchased was usually around 5% of net income. Since then, it has ranged between 25 and 47% of net income. An important question concerns why this change in repurchases occurred. The data suggests that dividends as a proportion of net income did not decrease to compensate for the increase in repurchases. In a careful study, Dunsby [1993] finds some evidence of a small substitution of repurchases for dividends but this does not appear to be very significant. Instead, the increase in repurchases appears to correspond to an increase in the overall level of payouts. It is notable that the other major form of payout from the corporate to private sector, namely mergers and acquisitions, also increased dramatically during the mid 1980s.

The third observation is that individuals pay substantial taxes on the large amounts they receive in dividends. Peterson, Peterson & Ang [1985] conducted an extensive study of the tax returns of individuals in 1979. More than \$33 billion was included in gross income that year. Data shows that the total amount of dividends paid out by corporations in 1979 was \$52 billion, so individuals received over two-thirds of the total. The average marginal tax rate on these dividends received by individuals (weighted by dividends received) was 40%. Most dividends were received by individuals in high tax brackets.

The fact that individuals pay large amounts of taxes on dividends has been particularly important in the dividend debate, because there is a substantial tax disadvantage to dividends

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compared to repurchases. When dividends are received by shareholders, they are taxed as ordinary income. Before the implementation of the 1986 Tax Reform Act (TRA), share repurchases were taxed on a capital gains basis. Since the tax rate on capital gains was significantly lower than the tax rate on ordinary income, this meant there was a substantial advantage to repurchasing. Even after the 1986 TRA, which equalized the tax rate on capital gains and dividend income, there was a tax disadvantage to dividends: the basis of repurchased shares is not taxed, so the tax liability is effectively postponed. If stocks are held for the long term, this advantage can be substantial. Under the current tax code, individual investors' marginal tax rate on capital gains income is at most 28%, while the highest marginal tax rate on dividend income is 39.6%. The fact that large amounts of taxes are paid on dividends despite the existence of another, relatively untaxed, payout method has been termed the 'dividend puzzle' by Black [1976].

The fourth observation is that corporations smooth dividends. For the largest U.S corporations the dividends were stable for long periods of time, particularly in the 1950s and 1960s. Dividends are usually increased gradually and are rarely cut.

In a classic study, Lintner [1956] showed that this behavior was fairly widespread. He started with over 600 listed companies and selected 28 to survey and interview. These companies were not selected as a statistically representative sample, but were chosen to encompass a wide range of different situations. Lintner made a number of important observations concerning the dividend policies of these firms. The first is that firms are primarily concerned with the stability of dividends. They do not set dividends *de novo* each quarter. Instead, they first consider whether any change from the existing rate is necessary. Only when they have decided a change is necessary do they consider how large it should be. Managers appear to believe strongly that the market puts a premium on firms with a stable dividend policy.

Second, Lintner observed that earnings were the most important determinant of any change in dividends. Management needed to explain to shareholders the reason for its actions, and needed to

base its explanations on observable indicators. The level of earnings is the most important of these. Most companies appeared to have a target payout ratio; if there was a sudden unexpected increase in earnings, firms adjusted their dividends slowly. Firms were very reluctant to cut dividends.

Lintner's third finding was that dividend policy was set first. Other policies were then adjusted, taking dividend policy as given. For example, if investment opportunities were abundant and the firm had insufficient internal funds, it would resort to raising outside funds.

The fifth observation is that market reacts positively to announcements of dividend increases and negatively to announcement of dividend decreases. This phenomenon was documented by many studies such as Pettit [1972], Charest [1978], and Aharony & Swary [1980]. This evidence is consistent with markets in which managers know more than outside shareholders [e.g., Bhattacharya, 1979, or Miller & Rock, 1985], or when contracts are incomplete as suggested by Grossman & Hart [1982], Jensen [1986] and Easterbrook [1984].

3. Theoretical aspects

The first step towards understanding dividend policy is to recognize that the phrase means different things to different people. Therefore we must start by defining what we mean by it.

A firm's decisions about dividends are often mixed up with other financing and investment decisions. Some firms pay low dividends because management is optimistic about the firm's future and wishes to retain earnings for expansion. In this case the dividend is a by-product of the firm's capital budgeting decision. Another firm might finance capital expenditures largely by borrowing. This releases cash for dividends. In this case the firm's dividend is a by-product of the borrowing decision.

We must isolate dividend policy from other problems of financial management. The precise question we should ask is: "What is the effect of a change in cash dividends paid, *given the firm's capital budgeting and borrowing decisions*?" Of course the cash used to finance a dividend

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increase has to come from somewhere. If we fix the firm's investment outlays and borrowing, there is only one possible source -- an issue of stock. Thus we define dividend policy as the trade-off between retaining earnings on the one hand and paying out cash and issuing new shares on the other.

This trade-off may seem artificial at first, for we do not observe firms scheduling a stock issue with every dividend payment. But there are many firms that pay dividends and also issue stock from time to time. They could avoid the stock issues by paying lower dividends. Many other firms restrict dividends so that they do not have to issue shares. They could issue stock occasionally and increase the dividend. Both groups of firms are facing the dividend policy trade-off.

Dividend policy along with the management of capital structure causes essential impact on the share price of a firm. Dividends are essentially money income of shareholders and to a certain extent signalize them about the performance of a firm to which they have put their money. Simplified scheme of profit allocation can be presented in the following way: part of the profit is paid in the form of dividends, the residual is reinvested in the assets of enterprise. Reinvested part of the profit is internal source of financing enterprise activity, that is why it is obvious that dividend policy determines the size of external borrowing.

Reinvestment of profits is more reasonable and relatively more inexpensive of financing enterprise activity, which is growing its scope. That is one of the causes why it is so frequently met. An afterwar research conducted by British scholars which included about four hundred companies registered in the London Stock Exchange and coming from production, trade, construction and transport has shown that new investment projects were financed up to 91% out of retained earnings.

Reinvestment of profits allows for evading from extra expenditures which have place when new shares are issued. Another substantial advantage is sustainment of existing system of control over the enterprise activity, because in this case the number of shareholders practically does not change.

From theoretical point of view the choice of dividend policy presumes the solution of the two following key issues:

- *Does the quantity of dividends paid has any impact on shareholders' wealth?*
- *And if so what is the optimal size dividend paid*

3.1 Opposing approaches

There is a controversial question of how dividend policy affects value. One endearing feature of economics is that it can always accommodate not just two, but three opposing points of view. And so it is with the controversy about dividend policy. On the right side there is a conservative group which believes that an increase in dividend payout increases firm value. On the left, there is a radical group which believes that an increase in payout reduces value. And in the center there is a middle-of-the-road party which claims that dividend policy makes no difference.

3.1.1 Dividend policy is irrelevant in Perfect Capital Markets

The challenge to financial economists has been to develop a dividend policy framework based on firms maximizing profits and investors maximizing utility, that is consistent with these observations and is not rejected by careful empirical tests. The seminal contribution to research on dividend policy was Miller & Modigliani [1961]. Prior to their paper, it was widely accepted that the more dividends a firm paid, the more valuable the firm would be. This view was derived from an extension of the discounted dividends approach to firm valuation, which says that the value V_0 of the firm at date 0, if the first dividends are paid one period from now at date 1, is given by the formula:

$$V_0 = \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \frac{D_t}{(1+r_t)^t}$$

Where D_t = the dividends paid by the firm at the end of period t ,

r_t = the investors' opportunity cost of capital for period t .

Gordon [1959] argued that the investor's required rate of return r_t would increase as a result of increased retention of earnings. Although the future dividend stream would presumably be larger as a result of the increase in investment (i.e., D_t would grow faster), he felt that higher r_t would overshadow this effect. The reason for the increase in r_t would be higher uncertainty concerning cash flows due to delaying the dividend stream.

Miller & Modigliani pointed out that this view of dividend policy was flawed, and they developed a rigorous framework for analyzing dividend policy. This framework has formed the foundation of subsequent work on dividends. Miller and Modigliani [1961] show that, under the assumption of perfect capital markets and rational behavior, the dividend policy is irrelevant in a corporate-profit-tax-free world.

In the Miller-Modigliani model, the dividend policy is irrelevant because all investors are indifferent with respect to the choice between a dividend and a capital gain share. According to the Miller-Modigliani model, dividend paying shares will sell at the same price as capital gains shares (if there is no tax to be paid on the dividends). Dividends and capital gains are then perfect substitutes as sources of income for shareholders. Thus, if new issuance costs and corporate or personal taxes are considered, Miller-Modigliani's proposition implies that managers will likely adopt a residual dividend policy. That is to say, dividends will be paid only if all positive NPV investment opportunities are exhausted (Higgins [1972]). Such a residual policy will result in an unstable dividend policy. In a Miller-Modigliani world, there is:

-No agency cost, that is to say conflicts of interests among managers, stockholders, bondholders do not appear;

-No taxes on corporate or individual incomes on shares and no taxes on capital gains;

-No asymmetric information between managers and the financial markets;

-No relationship between investment, financing decisions and dividend question.

But, we observe that many investors do receive dividends; among them some prefer high dividend yielding shares. See the stylized facts above.

Financial analysts point out two factors for explaining such a situation. First of all, the discounted value of year dividends is higher than the present value worth of distant capital gains. Second, as Graham et al. [1961] wrote in an old and classic textbook: "between two companies with the same general earning power and the same position in an industry, the one paying the larger dividend will always sell at a higher price". Using a questionnaire, *Partington* [1985] analyzed motives for paying dividends. The main responses are shown in Table 31-1. As in *Lintner* [1956], the analysis suggests that dividends are fixed on a non-residual basis. The desire to satisfy shareholders and support the share price, and the motive for indicating future profitability appears as the primary motivations for paying dividends.

Table 1

Motives for Paying Dividends

Source: Partington [1985]

(Sample Size: 84)

Rank	Motives	Percentage of Firms responding		
		Not Important	Slightly or Moderately Important	Important or very Important
(1)	To meet shareholder requirement for income	8.7	20.6	70.6
(2)	To maintain shareholder loyalty	3.3	33.7	63.1
(3)	To support or increase company's share	7.6	38.0	54.4
(4)	To indicate to shareholders the management view of the firm's future profitability	16.6	37.8	46.7
(5)	To make it easier to raise external finance in the future	18.7	38.5	42.9
(8)	Because of a shortage sufficiently profitable opportunities for reinvestment of retained earnings	92.1	5.6	2.2
(9)	To reduce surplus liquid assets	94.4	5.6	0.0

According to Jensen and Meckling [1976], and the agency costs theory, management has always an incentive to consume perquisites (as a big office, a costly company car, etc.) out of undistributed profits. In addition, management may invest suboptimally the retained earnings. Increasing dividend payments is a way for solving these agency problems because it reduces free cash-flow for perquisites. As less internal funds are available, needs to go to the capital market are going to increase. And for succeeding in issuing new funds (equity or bond), management has to release outstanding information about the results of past investment policy. As a result the possibility of suboptimal investment is expected to decrease.

As management enjoys more information about their firm's future prospects with respect to new investment projects than any other outside claimants, they have to signal their favorable information. Issuing a dividend is perhaps the least costly device for signaling such information. If this asymmetric information exists, the share prices are going to be undervalued. If dividend signaling is credible, then share prices should increase as more dividends are paid, as this information asymmetry between management and the shareholders should vanish. Of course, the information asymmetry is expected to vary from one firm to another, and the optimal payout of dividend as signals will also be different among firms. Many empirical studies show that an increase in dividends brings a statistically significant increase in share prices. Also, any dividend decrease registers a far greater negative price impact. The classic interpretation is that managers are reluctant to cut dividends: a dividend decrease is more informative than a dividend increase.

4. Data and methodology

4.1 Data

The database of the Russian companies was set up by me in the framework of the project "Financial markets in economies in transition." The database includes a complete set of various indicators of Russian companies, such as complete balance sheets, profit and loss statements, ownership structures, number of issued shares and many others. The data collected came from the annual 1996 report of Brunswick brokerage house and proved out to be a reliable and invaluable source of data for the project which is very important taking into account difficulties many researches are now facing in Russia while trying to obtain data.

The database itself offers indicators for four subsequent years starting from 1993 when Russian stock market started to emerge. The time interval may appear to be very small for reasonable analysis, but there seems to be not much can be done upon it. While in the West there are long financial series being available, we have quite short ones and this just adds to the specifics and complexity of the problem.

The database was extended by calculation of various indicators pertinent to the investigation of dividend policy, such as dividend ratios and variance coefficients for the profits. The concentration index was kindly offered to me by Alexey Zhiltsov who investigated its influence on the price of the shares.

The data about stock prices came from Skate Press information agency. The part of database used in the research consists of daily stock prices for 50 Russian companies. The time range is from January 1995 to January 1997. All the series were constructed to take into account split effects on the price of shares.

The price series were redefined to reflect the consistency with dividend payments, because price series are in daily terms, while dividends are paid on the annual basis. For this reason prices were averaged over the year.

4.2 Methodology

4.2.1 Resolving the controversy: do dividends influence price?

Perhaps the major issue which comes up when we start dealing with dividend policy is whether it has or not any impact on the behavior of the share price of the company. The controversy of this lies in the existence of controversial approaches to the subject. As MM pointed out dividend policy is irrelevant, that is the policy of whether to pay dividends and how to pay them is a residual one and has no impact. But MM approach has a lot of assumptions which should be subject to check when we come to reality. These assumptions may be violated even in Western financial markets and become even more critical in Russia. The basic assumptions in MM theory are about perfect and complete financial markets.

Obviously Russian stock market is far away from being complete because not all securities are traded and there are many securities which are traded but illiquid. There are about fifteen so called Blue Chips stocks which are traded actively and can be considered the most liquid ones in Russia. Stocks which are not so liquid as Blue Chips but moving towards it are so-called Second Tier Blue Chips. And finally we have the rest of the shares which are traded only infrequently or not traded at all.

Another critical assumption concerns agency costs. MM assumption is that there is no agency cost, that is there is no conflict of interests among managers, stockholders and bondholders. In Russia this is especially vibrant issue because these conflicts are rather acute, especially between managers and shareholders. There were cases when large shareholders simply could not get to the meeting of shareholders to realize their voting rights, because managers did not want them to.

Absence of taxes and symmetric information are also dubious assumptions. Because taxes are present and information is asymmetric it can have big impact on the validity of MM conclusions.

4.2.2 The impact of profit volatility on dividend policy

One of the factors that can influence firm's dividend policy is a volatility of profits a firm is facing. The idea here is that volatile profits can have negative impact on the amount of dividends paid out of profits. Having volatile profits a firm has an uncertainty about the amount of financing which will be available in the form of retained earnings. Thus a firm can face a high interest rate if realized profit turned out to be low and it has to go to market for loans which can be extremely expensive relative to the expected returns on investment. Presumably higher volatility associated with profits will lead a firm to a decision of lowering its dividend payments and increasing retained earnings to hedge against risk associated with uncertainty about future profits.

In order to track the impact of profit volatility on dividend policy a variance coefficient was used as a proxy. Variance coefficient is a ratio of standard deviation of profit to the mean over the time interval. It was computed for each firm and incorporated into the model.

4.2.3 The impact of ownership structure on dividend policy

Ownership structure can have a significant effect on a firm's performance. And it turned out to be especially acute factor which can explain many things. Ideally a firm should have a lot of shareholders, each of them having negligible impact on control over a firm. Due to the fact that in Russia we usually have large stockholders, both among managers and employees on one side and institutional investors on the other, ownership structure can become important. As it was shown for instance by Zhiltsov in his Master's thesis (see NES Master's theses 1997), concentration of ownership claims can have impacts both on the firms' performance and stock price. He has found curvilinear relationship between the concentration of outside investors and performance—stock price. At low level of outside control the relationship is positive and becomes negative after a certain point.

From all this the idea came to investigate the impact of ownership structure on the dividend policy. The impact have unpredictable direction from theoretical point of view. There are two opposing forces at work and the total effect depends upon the dominance of one of them.

The first argument goes like this. If the share of outside investors goes up, the share of insiders obviously goes down. So the managers of a company are more afraid of a possibility of a takeover and them being subsequently fired. So they have to pay to support the price of the share, which can make the takeover more expensive and to decrease the possibility of it. In this argument concentration of outsiders has positive impact on amount paid in dividends. But this argument appeals to the Gordon's theory that dividends have positive impact on share price and which is the opponent to MM contribution.

Second argument is based upon the willingness of outside shareholders to have more investment now, so there will be fruits of this investment in the future. This naturally leads to the reduction in the amount of dividends paid now and to an increase in the amount of retained earnings for investment. So the more the outside investors have the claims on the firm, so that the larger the number of shares held by outsiders, the more able they are to execute control over the firm's decisions and the more they will invest and pay lower amount in dividends. This argument does not appeal to any assumptions about which theory of the impact of dividend policy on the stock price is correct.

4.2.4 The impact of tax evasion motive on dividend policy

The idea of tax evasion motive naturally comes to mind if we take into account Russian reality. Because the situation with tax collection is very difficult in Russia due to the poor Tax code and to people being not very eager to pay them to finance government expenditures. The situation is worsened by the inability of the government to enforce firms to pay taxes. In such a situation tax evasion can explain a lot of what is happening in the Russian economy.

The argument of the tax evasion impact on dividend policy goes like follows. If a firm evades, it has to understate its tax base, with profits serving as a proxy for that. In order to conceal its profits a firm should prevent any information about "true" profit to leak. Because higher profits are usually associated with higher dividend payments, a firm should probably pay less dividends and to retain more. Thus the more a firm evades from taxes, the less it should pay dividends.

4.2.5 A Model of Corporate Dividend Policy

Econometric testing in finance is mainly carried out using time series or cross section data. The availability of long time series of disaggregated price data partially explains this phenomenon. Very little empirical work for testing capital asset pricing models, for instance, has been done using panel data methods. Early studies, which have used panel data in finance, have mainly concentrated on dividends. In finance, empirical testing relies mostly on firm specific samples limited to stock market quoted firms. As Bond and Meghir [1987] suggest: "A sample of exclusively quoted firms is non random, since firms may only receive a stock market listing if they satisfy specified criteria and even they may choose to remain unquoted". As a matter of fact, this decision, to be officially quoted or not, can be controlled by allowing for fixed effects.

Because of the above difficulties related to the infant state of the Russian stock market and to the shortness of financial series a more elaborated methodology than simple time series probably should be applied. Having data for many companies and for short time period the idea of using panel data analysis naturally comes into one's mind. Panel data analysis is a powerful tool which can allow to use not only cross section or time series variation, but both of them. Below a panel data model of dividend policy is given.

Even if we ignore tax considerations, *Rozeff* [1983] puts forward that the dividend payout ratio should be explained by costs of raising external funds and agency costs.

We suggest that the payout ratio is set by management so there is a trade-off between advantages of dividends as a signaling device and agency costs. Payment of dividends is assumed to be the least-costly way for quoted firms to solve asymmetric and agency problems. So, the signaling constraint implies a relation between any dividend change and information that management wishes to release.

As managers are reluctant to cut dividends, the dividend is related to management's rational expectations of future net earnings. Any change in dividends must imply a change in information that insiders have and managers sidestep, making changes in dividend payments if they will have to be canceled later.

We assume that the management of firm I, for period t , determines a target dividend payout ratio as the following:

$$D^*_{it} = \beta X^p_{it},$$

Where X^p_{it} defines long run expected earning.

We now consider the following result from Flavin [1981]:

$$X_{it} = (1+r) \sum_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+r} \right)^{j+1} E_t X_{it+j+1} - \sum_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+r} \right)^{j+1} E_t X_{it+j+1}.$$

After some algebraic manipulations, the following results are obtained:

$$X^p_{it} = (1+r)X^p_{it-1} - \gamma X_{it}.$$

As the new debt financing allows agency monitoring of the dividend policy (*John and Kalay* [1982]), the dividend adjustment equation for firm I is obtained:

$$D_{it} - D_{it-1} = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2(D^*_{it} - D_{it-1}) - \lambda_3 nb_{it} + \omega_i + \upsilon_{it},$$

Where NB is the new flow for current period t of long term debt. We allow for firm specific effects.

This firm effect can be viewed as a firm's component of the "normal" signaling constraint which all quoted firms must satisfy. The constant term is added to account for the fact that managers are reluctant to cut dividends.

Rearranging terms, one derives the company dividend equation:

$$D_{IT} = \lambda_1 + D_{IT-1} \left[1 + \lambda_2 \left(1 - \frac{(1+r)}{\beta} \right) \right] - \lambda_2 \gamma X_{it} - \lambda_3 NB_{it} + \omega_I + v_{it}.$$

If we follow *Blundell et al.* [1987], the correct assumptions need to be made about the stochastic process which generates X_{it} , as the consistency of the estimators in the last equation relies upon this. If X_{it} is assumed to be predetermined rather than strictly exogenous, then one only has to use instrumental variables' methods on the difference model since within group estimators suffer from biases in standard dynamic panel models (see *Nickel* [1981]). Here we follow *Arellano and Bond* [1991] and use a two-step Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator. Monte-Carlo results, for balanced and unbalanced data sets, using the GMM estimators, indicate good performance with negligible finite sample biases and smaller variance than with other procedures.

The GMM estimator for the k coefficients in last equation are given by:

$$\hat{\delta} = (X'ZA_NZ'X)^{-1} (X'ZA_NZ'y),$$

where X is the $(T-2)N \times k$ matrix of observations. When X_{it} is assumed to be predetermined, we have:

$$E(X_{it}v_{is}) \begin{cases} = 0 & \text{if } s < t, \\ \neq 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then, only $X_{it}, \dots, X_{it-2}$ are appropriate instruments in the difference equation. *Arellano and Bond* [1991] discuss optimal choice for A_N with v_{it} independent and heteroscedastic both across units and over time. If we neglect NB , the instrument set for firm I is given by:

$$Z_i \begin{pmatrix} X_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & D_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & X_1 & X_2 & \dots & & & 0 & D_1 & D_2 & \dots & & & \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & X_1 & \dots & X_{T-2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & D_1 & D_{T-2} \end{pmatrix}$$

5. Stylized facts for the dividend policy of Russian companies.

The peculiarities of Russian stock markets are clearly seen in the application of the above mentioned stylized facts to the Russian reality. Below each stylized is analyzed for the robustness in the explanation of the stock prices and financial indicators of Russian firms.

5.1 First fact:

The first stylized fact for industrially developed countries is that corporations typically pay out a significant amount of their earnings in the form of dividends. The estimates show that in recent years U. S corporations have paid between 50% and 70% of their after tax profits in dividend form.

The fact was reconsidered to be applied to Russian companies. The same ratio was calculated for major Russian companies (selected on the basis of liquidity and capitalization share in total stock market). The number of companies selected is equal to 65, with the total capitalization value of 35.5 bln.\$. The dividend payment ratio was calculated with dividends equal to total payments both for common and preferred shares (weighted by the share of both types). Net after tax profits were taken as a proxy for earnings. Than dividend payment ratio was averaged for four years (from 1993 to 1996). Finally individual dividend payment ratios were averaged taken the account the market share of the companies (which is the share of capitalization in total market).

Valery S. Manokhin, "Dividend policy in Russia", NES Master's thesis, 1997
The figure computed is dividend payment ratio equal to 14.2%, which is significantly lower
that for the U. S economy.

This can be partly explained by the infant state of Russian stock market. As U. S history shows dividend payments were growing steadily over time.

5.2 Second fact:

Historically, dividends have been the predominant form of payout; share repurchases were relatively unimportant until the mid 1980s.

As for the Russia the fact seems to be controversial. Taken into account lower dividend payment ratio, it seems that agents hold stocks for speculative motives.

5.3 Third fact:

Individuals in high tax brackets receive large amounts in dividends and pay substantial amount of taxes on these dividends.

According to current U. S tax code individual investors' marginal tax rate on capital gains income is at most 28%, while the highest marginal tax rate on dividend income is 39.6%.

In Russia the current tax code is as follows;

	<i>Capital gains</i>	<i>Dividends</i>
<i>Legal entities</i>	35%	35%
<i>Individuals</i>	12% and higher	15%

The figures show that in Russia there are more favorable tax conditions for individual investors, although tax rate for corporate investors being close to overseas ones.

5.4 Forth fact:

Corporations smooth out dividends. Dividends are usually stable for long periods of time. They are usually increased gradually and are rarely cut. For example in 1992 year 78% of selected U. S firms increased dividends and only 22% decreased on not paid them. Shown below is a pie chart for the pattern of dividend behavior. It clearly shows that more than half of Russian firms increased payments over time, although this figure is lower than for the U. S economy.

Also shown below is the pattern behavior of dividend payments over time. The dividend payment ratio for each year is a weighted average on the basis of market share. As picture clearly shows dividends were growing steadily over time from about 5% of net profits to near 30%. We may expect future growth and convergence to the figures in industrial countries as Russian stock market matures over time.

6. Who and how pays dividends: sectors comparison

It is interesting to look at the issue how the sector to which enterprise belongs to influences its dividend policy. A priori we can hypothesize that more prosperous enterprises in such sectors as oil&gas, ferrous and non-ferrous, which are raw materials sectors of the economy will have to pay less dividends to retain profit for investment projects. These projects need to be undertaken to meet domestic and export demand for their products. These sectors also face the problem of replacing existing capital stock as it depreciates over time and to develop new extraction methods.

6.1 Oil&gas, ferrous and non ferrous metals

These sectors have declining pattern of dividend policy. The dividend ratio in these sectors declined steadily over the time. The pattern may be explained by several factors. First of them was mentioned above, namely that while these companies were facing sufficient demand both from domestic customers and from abroad, they needed to replace capital stock which depreciated over time. Because equipment is very expensive for these sectors, they needed to retain more earnings to finance its purchases. Another reason is that perhaps they the managers of the companies did not have to sustain the price of their shares as they become more popular over time. And perhaps the most important reason lies in the tax evasion motive.

Because these companies pay substantial amounts in the form of taxes, they may be reluctant to show how profitable they are and pay less dividends.

6.2 Power and telecoms

These companies enjoyed tremendous success recently. Facing steady demand they were able to remain profitable in the overall recession in Russia. The stock prices were moving upward and allowed investors to harvest huge capital gains. In the aspect of dividend policy these companies were increasing their dividend ratio and if we accept the influence of dividend payments on stock price behavior it could contribute to the success of these companies.

6.3 Pulp and paper, automotive and shipping

Like those of raw material sector, companies from pulp and paper, automotive and shipping were decreasing their dividend payments over time. Being the most favorable shares to hold at the early stages of the Russian stock market development, they are now in the end of the list.

6.4 Consumer goods and engineering

These sectors were extremely hurt in the macroeconomic recession in Russia. Facing strong competition from abroad, they have experienced tremendous difficulties in adapting their activities to new market type environment. Looking at their dividend payments pattern, we see unusual ones. Contrary to any theory, these companies have unstable dividend payments. And it seems that these companies do not have any dividend policy at all. They either pay a lot if they are profitable, or little if they are not.

6.5 Implications

Having considered the impact of industry on the dividend policy, a rough conclusion can be derived from it, namely that dividend policy do has effects on stock price behavior.

This is based upon the relation between dividend payments over time and the behavior of stock prices across sectors. At it seems that Russian companies do have a kind of dividend policy, except for those from consumer goods and engineering. Patterns of dividend policies are given in Appendix.

7. Results

7.1 Dividend policy: Russian evidence

Here the evidence is given to the issue of which factors determine dividend policy of a Russian company. I first compute simple correlation coefficients between the amount of dividends paid and other factors which can influence this variable.

Below the simple statistics is given about the variables able to explain dividend policy of Russian companies.

Descriptive statistics

Means

div94	Constant	div93	pr93	pr94	debt94	Index	Variance
16.56	1.000	40.67	133.2	160.3	65.00	0.2265	0.4622

Standard Deviations

div94	Constant	div93	pr93	pr94	debt94	Index	Variance
41.69	0.0000	78.28	446.2	580.6	170.4	0.1576	0.6335

Correlation matrix

	div94	Constant	div93	pr93	pr94	debt94	Index	Variance
div94	1.00							
Constant	0.00	1.00						
div93	0.47	0.00	1.00					
pr93	-0.03	0.00	-0.09	1.00				
pr94	-0.03	0.00	-0.12	0.98	1.00			
debt94	-0.145	0.00	-0.23	0.83	0.81	1.00		
Index	-0.47	0.00	-0.44	-0.17	-0.11	0.04	1.00	
Variance	-0.16	0.00	-0.59	-0.04	-0.03	0.15	0.24	1.00

Correlation coefficients were calculated over the cross section of the sample of Russian companies. Among the factors able to explain the dividend policy the following variables were chosen:

According to Lintner [1956] argument previous year dividend payments were included. This appeals to the fact that companies do not set dividend payments *de novo* each year but are trying to adjust from the preceding year's. The factor of lagged dividends turned out to have significant effects in the determination of today's dividend policy of a firm.

Current period profits were also chosen as one of the factors of interest. The correlation of current dividend payments turned out to be negative. This may seem as a surprising result, however we should take into account that this effect is perhaps insignificant as evidenced by its size, and another reason is that probably more profitable companies in the sample do prefer to pay less dividends even in absolute size. These are basically companies from raw materials sector we are investing aggressively into new capital and are trying to retain profits for this purpose.

Last period profits were also included, according to argument given by Nakamura and Nakamura [1985]. The effect turned out to be of predicted sign but may be insignificant.

Among the other variables of interest is an amount of long term debt which a company attracts to finance its expenditures. As the new debt financing allows agency monitoring of the dividend policy (John and Kalay [1982]), it also should be chosen as one of the factors. This factor turned out to have a significant effect on dividend policy and of right sign.

Index of concentration of outside investors has the impact of the order compared to last dividends one. It was calculated as Herfindahl like type of index, namely as sum of the squares of the shares held by outside investors. The negative sign of it supports the idea that as the share of outside investors goes up, they are able to influence the company decisions to a more full extent, and as

outside investors want to invest more, the amount of retained earnings goes up and dividends naturally go down.

Volatility of profits is the last factor chosen for explanation. Like exactly a theory suggested is does have effects on the dividends paid, so companies are using dividend policy as a hedge against the risk associated with uncertain profits and the possibility of borrowing in the future at higher interest rates.

All these factors were incorporated into the model which is trying to explain the amount paid in dividends. The results of this estimation are given in Appendix.

7.2 Is Modigliani - Miller wrong?

Perhaps the most important issue which naturally arises when managers of a company are trying to formulate lies in the ability of dividend policy to influence the price of a stock. The research in this area was very fruitful, but the result is that it has controversial implications. In this paper the MM hypothesis was tested which has to do with the irrelevance of dividend policy.

In order to test this hypothesis a regression of a proxy for price earning ration was regressed on the number of factors. In order to deal with price earnings ratio being unavailable to compute because earnings may be zero for a certain period of time, earnings were taken to be net profit, a reverse ratio was constructed, which can be called "earnings-price ratio". The solution was that price of a stock in non zero for obvious reasons.

In order to explain variations in price earnings ratio, a series of ten industry dummies were included into regression, because price earnings ratio depends to a great extent upon the industry to which company belongs to. For instance companies from more profitable sectors should have lower price ratio.

Although there are many factors except sector to which company belongs to that can determine price earnings ratio, only one of them, namely dividend policy was chosen for consideration. Endogenous variable (earnings price ratio) was regressed on dividend policy.

The result was that that dividend policy still matters for stock price performance, although the effect may be not very big. Accordingly MM were wrong with the conclusion that dividend policy has nothing to do with stock price behavior. This may stem from very strong assumption in MM theory upon the completeness and perfectness of securities markets in Russia, but may also be due to the other factors as well.

The implication for this is that managers of companies firms have to seriously consider dividend policy which they are going to follow, because it can have effects on the performance of the firm and on its stock price. Consequently it can have effects on the ability of managers to borrow to finance firm's operations, both domestic and from abroad. This is especially pertinent to current situation in Russia where companies are trying to borrow to replace existing capital stock and to finance new investment projects.

The results of the estimation are given in the appendix. We observe that earnings price ratio is positively correlated with this year dividend payments and negatively correlated with last year dividend payments. This basically means that payment of dividends has positive lagged effect of stock price.

7.3 Evidence: a model of corporate dividend policy

In order to fully exploit the nature of the data available, a panel data model was employed for empirical analysis of dividend policy of Russian firms.

The conclusions of this model support the conclusions made by employing less sophisticated econometrics, but seems to be more reliable due to the lack of biases in estimates of coefficients in appropriate panel data methodology.

The basic factors turned out to have effects on the dividend policy were as follows. Like simple Lintner model predicts, companies are trying to make themselves oriented on last year dividend payments, so this year dividends are set looking one the previous ones. Among other factors which have impact on dividend policy are current and last year profits, and the amount of long term debt a company attracts for financing its operations.

All factors turned to have reasonable signs, for instance dividends are positively correlated with today's profits and so on. The results of panel data estimation are given in the Appendix together with developments up to the model in the class of behavioral models of dividend policy.

8. Conclusions and implications

In this paper the research concentrated on the dividend policy with applications to Russian securities markets. A number of issues were raised for empirical investigation. Perhaps the major one of them was resolving the dividend controversy on empirical level upon the issue whether dividends are irrelevant as it is stated in Modigliani-Miller conclusions. This issue was subject to empirical analysis which has shown that MM is wrong and that dividend policy does have impact on the performance of companies and stock price. This has an implication for the managers of the company that dividend policy a company chooses is an important and vibrant issue which can have long term effects related to the financing of the investment projects.

Another issue raised was the dividend policy per se. The factors which can have impact on dividend policy were focused on and analyzed. Among the most important factors influencing the dividend policy were the sector in which a company operates and which can have long run effects on the dividend payment pattern.

Factors which can effect short run decisions upon the dividend policy were the decisions made in the past together with current indicators of performance, such as current profit and the amount of long term debt a company attracts for financing.

Structure of ownership turned out to be a significant factor influencing the company's policy in all aspects and dividend policy in particular. The analysis has shown that concentration of outside investors has negative effect on the amount of dividends paid. The underlying reasoning is that these outside shareholders are able to execute control over the company to a more full extent when their stake grow and are willing to retain profits to pursue attractive investment opportunities, which leads to a reduction in dividends.

Appendix:

Who and how pays dividends: intersectoral comparison

Dividend policy: The results of cross section estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-value	t-prob
Constant	24.770	28.460	0.870	0.4045
div93	0.26537	0.18423	1.440	0.1803
pr93	-0.13920	0.15721	-0.885	0.3967
pr94	0.10361	0.11010	0.941	0.3688
debt94	0.0057150	0.12315	0.046	0.9639
Index	-104.60	80.501	-1.299	0.2230

Is Modigliani-Miller wrong: empirical results

Correlation matrix

Power	Ferrous	Non-Ferrous	Shipping	Pulp	Auto	Cons	News	Eng	Div(-1)
-0.02	0.16	0.05	-0.04	0.00	0.04	-0.07	-0.04	0.24	-0.03

Is Modigliani-Miller wrong: results of regression analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-value	t-prob
Constant	0.095862	0.22064	0.434	0.6657
Power	0.21224	0.39994	0.531	0.5979
Ferrous	0.67196	0.52580	1.278	0.2068
Non-ferrous	0.14632	0.67462	0.217	0.8291
Shipping	0.12476	0.65634	0.190	0.8500

<i>Pulp</i>	0.28520	0.57860	0.493	0.6241
<i>Auto</i>	0.41672	0.57974	0.719	0.4754
<i>Consumer</i>	-0.093742	0.52655	-0.178	0.8594
<i>News</i>	-0.012529	1.0940	-0.011	0.9909
<i>Engineer</i>	1.4495	0.65617	2.209	0.0315
<i>div(-1)</i>	-0.0012391	0.0032350	-0.383	0.7032

Evidence: a model of corporate dividend policy

<i>Var</i>	<i>Coef</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>T-Stat</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
CONST	14.560318	7.480302	1.946488	0.051596
div-1	0.496301	0.260902	1.902250	0.057139
prof	0.015556	0.013286	1.170871	0.241651
debt	-0.043400	0.042073	-1.031533	0.302291
D95	2.544742	7.542389	0.337392	0.735821
I2	-12.154306	6.029685	-2.015745	0.043827
I3	29.245633	23.823745	1.227583	0.219603
I4	-13.051827	8.744855	-1.492515	0.135564
I5	6.086105	30.734755	0.198020	0.843029
I6	-15.778406	5.294922	-2.979913	0.002883
I7	-15.803207	5.610876	-2.816531	0.004855
I8	-10.308345	9.091345	-1.133864	0.256852
I9	1.635036	13.510740	0.121018	0.903677
I10	-15.863023	5.512647	-2.877569	0.004008
I11	-14.332282	5.400883	-2.653693	0.007962

Behavioral Models of Dividend Policy

Lintner [1956] uses field investigations to set up a partial adjustment model for explaining corporate dividend behavior. According to his findings, from the management point of view, the first question is not what amount of dividends should be paid, but whether the existing rate of payout should be modified. So, the dependent variable is the change in the existing rate.

Secondly, only partial adjustments in dividend rates should be made by management, partially reflecting the current earnings. Thirdly, Lintner observes general reluctance to cut dividend rates.

The partial adjustment framework can be summarized as:

$$D_t^* = \alpha Y_t, (1)$$

$$\text{and } D_t - D_{t-1} = \beta + \gamma(D_t^* - D_{t-1}) + v_t (2)$$

where D_t^* stands for the firm's optimal dividend payments, Y_t is the current net earnings and α is the target payout ratio. Derived from (1) and (2) Lintner's partial adjustment model takes the form:

$$\Delta D_t = \beta + \alpha \gamma Y_t - \gamma D_{t-1} + v_t (3)$$

The main problem with equation (1) is that the optimal dividend depends on current net earnings instead of those expected in the long run. Such an assumption may imply that dividend payments will fluctuate from period to period, which is counterfactual.

In the adaptive expectations framework, instead of equation (1), we assume now that dividends are related to expected long run net earnings

$$D_t = \alpha Y_t^* + \varepsilon_t, (4)$$

and that:

$$Y_t^* = \delta Y_t + (1-\delta)Y_{t-1}^*, (5)$$

where Y_t^* is the expected long run earnings, Y_t the observed earnings and δ is the coefficient measuring the permanent component of the earnings process.

Using (4) and (5), Lee et al. [1987] obtained:

$$\Delta D_t = \alpha \delta Y_t - \delta D_t + \varepsilon_t - (1-\delta)\varepsilon_{t-1}. (6)$$

Formulating expectations according to (3) is in fact more convenient for shareholders than for managers. Instead of (5), we should have current expectations of earnings derived from previous expectations in the light of the current dividend.

Still another alternative is given to (1) by Nakamura and Nakamura [1985] who suppose that management chooses the target dividend payment as:

$$D_t^* = \alpha Y_t^P, \quad (7)$$

Where Y_t^P is the permanent earnings as estimated by management; Y_t^P is given by:

$$Y_t^P = \gamma \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+r} \right)^{i+1} E_t(Y_{t+i+1}), \quad (8)$$

where E_t stands for mathematical expectations conditional on all information available at time t , r is the management time discount rate, and γ is the rate of return on the market value of the firm.

Current net earnings, not available to the market, are assumed to be known by the management.

The stochastic process for the earnings is assumed to be given by:

$$Y_{t+1} = Y_t + \delta + v_{t+1}, \quad (9)$$

where δ is a drift and v , a random term, which is normally distributed with zero mean over time. Nakamura and Nakamura show that substituting (8) and (9) into (2) gives:

$$\Delta D_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_t - \alpha_2 Y_{t-1} - \alpha_3 D_{t-1} + v_t - \alpha_4 v_t, \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ are parameters derived from coefficients of equations (3), (8) and (9).

We emphasize that α_1 , the coefficient of Y_t must be positive, and $(-\alpha_2)$, the coefficient of Y_{t-1} must be negative (whereas $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2$). In fact, (10) is a mixed model, denoted rational model by Nakamura and Nakamura, as it integrates partial adjustment and rational expectations. In this model the restrictions on coefficients are empirically testable.

The above models make no explicit reference as to the potential role of dividends as being signals by the insiders (management) of a firm. Equation (7) may do it in some way but, as King [1977] suggests, changes in the signal should be connected only with changes in expectations about the permanent earnings as estimated by management. Two questions then arise. First, should we use a partial adjustment model in parallel with signals adjusted to permanent earnings? Second, as investors pay tax on dividend incomes, is tax incurs in the cost of signaling, as suggested by *Feldstein and Green* [1980]?

Yet, following *Auerbach* [1979], we argue that firms must pay dividends to distribute cash income to their shareholders if share repurchases out of retentions is forbidden, as it is in a France.

Anderson advocates the use of a quadratic cost function such as:

$$[D_t - \alpha Y_t]^2 + \lambda_1 [D_t - D_{t-2}]^2 \quad (11)$$

The first term in (11) represents the costs of no signaling and the second term indicates the costs of changing the signal. Like *Anderson*, we could add any other empirical costs, such as departure from an optimal rate of internally financed investment expenditure or adjustment costs related to variable debt-equity ratio. However, we have no arguments for choosing such an adjustment costs function.

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